

LANGUAGE TEACHING BASED ON AN INTEGRATED APPROACH

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***Abstract.** The article is devoted to the current stage of development of the educational process, which is characterized by the desire to reproduce the culture accumulated by society in the content of education; discovery of humanistic ideas, common elements and traditions in the languages and cultures being studied; familiarization with the processes of globalization, interdependence of countries and peoples in modern conditions. It is logical to assume that communication in real communication will be difficult if one of the speech skills is not developed at a sufficient level. Thus, the development of communicative competence involves the integrated development of skills and abilities in all types of speech activity. The use of an integrative approach in teaching a foreign language becomes the “conceptual idea of a modern school.”*

***Key words:** communicative competence, motivation, integrative techniques, integrative approach in education, modernization of education, open system, competence, communicative competence.*

The education system today begins to function as an open system and becomes the sphere of manifestation and resolution of the basic contradictions of the society of the future. When teaching a foreign language, the teacher's efforts are always aimed at creating conditions for the development of students' communicative competence, since this is the main goal. The current stage of development of the educational process is characterized by a number of trends: the desire to reproduce the culture accumulated by society in the content of education; discovery of humanistic ideas, common elements and traditions in the languages and cultures being studied; familiarization with the processes of globalization, interdependence of countries and peoples in modern conditions; development of a didactic support system for the educational process. It should be noted that the goal of integrative learning is to contribute to the creation of a harmonious and holistic vision of the world, and turning to an integrative approach in education helps to form the organic integrity of the educational process.

The same skills that help a person navigate new situations in his professional, personal and social life, achieving his goals.

Goals are usually called competencies or key competencies. The traditional system in the form in which it exists has exhausted itself and through evolutionary means, through internal transformation, must move into a new qualitative state. The concepts of “knowledge”, “ability”, “skills” have been replaced by the term “competence”. Competence [German] kompetent - appropriate, capable] is the ability to solve a range of certain socially significant problems based on existing knowledge on this issue. Communicative competence includes mastery of all types of speech activity, the basics of the culture of oral and written speech, basic skills and abilities of using language in various areas and situations of communication. However, this concept includes not only mastering the necessary set of speech and language knowledge, but also the formation of skills in the field of practical use of language in the process of speech activity. This also correlates with the implementation of educational tasks in the formation of a socially active personality oriented in the modern world.

Communicative competence here becomes part of cultural competence, leading to an increase in the general humanitarian culture of the individual, the formation of high creative, ideological and behavioral qualities necessary for inclusion in various types of activities. Formation of communicative competence is a long and quite complex process. The ultimate goal of teaching within the framework of the communicative activity approach is the formation of students’ communicative competence in the unity of all its components: linguistic (knowledge of the language system), speech (knowledge of ways to form and formulate thoughts using language), sociocultural (students’ knowledge of the national and cultural characteristics of social and speech behavior of native speakers: their customs, etiquette, social stereotypes, history and culture, as well as ways of using this knowledge in communication process) and other competencies.

Since communicative competence presupposes mastering the ability to generate texts in various spheres of communication according to accepted canons, training should be subordinated to solving the main task - the reproduction and production of texts, that is, the formation of the ability to produce texts, mastery of textual techniques activities. Listening to recordings of questions and statements.

The conditions of real communication imply the development of the skill of taking notes under dictation. In this fragment, this skill is used to facilitate understanding of the questions and statements being asked, and relieves the load on students’ short-term memory. The final stage of the work can be students’ oral

statements in free form, based on statements about the text, which also stimulates the development of a variety of skills necessary in real communication.

This format of work allows you to organically integrate various types of speech activity in a foreign language lesson, which can bring communication closer to the conditions of real communication.

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